

A Compact Questionnaire for Evaluating Interactive Visualizations in AI-Literacy Education

Anonymous (author names omitted for double-blind review)

Supplementary instrument

Abstract

This document provides a short, reusable questionnaire for assessing how learners *perceive* an interactive visualization or hands-on artifact used to teach artificial-intelligence (AI) and machine-learning (ML) concepts. It captures perceived intuitiveness, clarity, understanding, interest, and educational usefulness, together with basic demographics and optional open-ended feedback. The instrument is deliberately compact so that it can be administered in informal settings such as exhibitions, workshops, or single classroom sessions. It measures *self-reported perceptions*, not knowledge gains; studies aiming to establish learning effects should complement it with objective pre-/post-tests. The questionnaire is released for free reuse and adaptation (see License).

1 Purpose and constructs

The instrument targets five perception constructs plus optional qualitative feedback. Table 1 maps each item to its construct.

Item	Construct	What it captures
1–4	Demographics	Age, gender, occupational field, prior AI experience
5	Perceived intuitiveness	Ease and naturalness of the interaction
6	Perceived clarity	Legibility of the presented information
7	Perceived understanding	Subjective sense of having understood the process
8	Interest / motivation	Influence on interest in AI and ML
9	Perceived usefulness	Suitability as a learning/teaching aid
10–12	Open feedback	Helpful aspects, improvements, further comments

Table 1: Mapping of questionnaire items to the constructs they measure.

2 Administration

- **Timing:** administer once, directly after the participant has interacted with the artifact (post-interaction design).
- **Scale:** rating items (5–9) use a five-point Likert scale on which higher values indicate a more positive evaluation (1 = lowest, 5 = highest).
- **Prior experience:** item 4 uses 1 = no experience to 5 = expert.

- **Optionality:** items 10–12 are optional free-text responses.
- **Ethics:** participation should be voluntary and anonymous, with no personal or identifying data collected.

3 Adaptation

The questionnaire is artifact-agnostic. To reuse it, replace “the LED wall” / “LED-Wall” with the name of your own visualization or artifact, and adjust item 8’s subject area if your topic is not AI/ML. The construct wording (intuitiveness, clarity, understanding, interest, usefulness) can be kept unchanged. The original wording below was used with an interactive LED-wall installation; it is reproduced verbatim for reproducibility.

4 Questionnaire (original wording)

The questionnaire was administered in German; the verbatim German wording is given below, with an English translation in italics.

Demografische Angaben (*Demographic information*)

1. Alter (*age*).
2. Geschlecht (*gender*).
3. In welcher Branche sind Sie tätig? (*occupational field; with free-text option*).
4. Vorerfahrung mit KI (*prior experience with AI*) (1 = keine Erfahrung / *no experience*, 5 = Experte / *expert*).

Bewertungsfragen (*rating items, five-point scale*)

5. Wie intuitiv fanden Sie die Interaktion mit der LED-Wall? (*How intuitive did you find the interaction with the LED wall?*)
6. Wie bewerten Sie die Klarheit der auf der LED-Wall dargestellten Informationen? (*How would you rate the clarity of the information presented on the LED wall?*)
7. Konnten Sie den KI-Trainingsprozess durch die Visualisierung besser verstehen? (*Did the visualization help you better understand the AI training process?*)
8. Hat die LED-Wall-Visualisierung Ihr Interesse an KI und maschinellem Lernen beeinflusst? (*Did the LED-wall visualization influence your interest in AI and machine learning?*)
9. Glauben Sie, dass die Visualisierung auf der LED-Wall ein Hilfsmittel für das Lernen/Lehren von KI ist? (*Do you believe that the visualization on the LED wall is a useful aid for learning and teaching AI?*)

Offene Fragen (optional) (*open-ended items, optional*)

10. Welche Aspekte der Visualisierung fanden Sie besonders hilfreich oder interessant? (*Which aspects of the visualization did you find particularly helpful or interesting?*)
11. Was könnten wir Ihrer Meinung nach verbessern, um die Erfahrung mit der LED-Wall zu optimieren? (*What could be improved to optimize the experience with the LED wall?*)

12. Haben Sie weitere Kommentare oder Anregungen zur LED-Wall oder zur Visualisierung des KI-Trainingsprozesses? (*Do you have any further comments or suggestions regarding the LED wall or the visualization of the AI training process?*)

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